

The first Trans-continental Networking Academy for
African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.

D1.1 Management and Quality Plan – Year 1

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
DM	Dissemination Manager
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IM	Innovation Manager
PC	Project Coordinator
QM	Quality Manager
SC	Steering Committee
SO	Specific Objectives
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Executive Summary

The Management and Quality Plan is intended to support partners in the effective and efficient administrative and financial management of the project while ensuring the quality of the project outcomes. It presents the procedures, structures and coordination defined to the project implementation and sets out key responsibilities for partners. It is intended to support the achievement of project objectives, the compliance with project scheduling and the timely delivery of project results.

AfriConEU Project will be ruled by the following principles for a Successful Project Management:

- ✓ Good communication between partners will be paramount to the success of the project.
- ✓ Ensure that more than one person in each partner organization is aware of what is going on in each of the specific tasks.
- ✓ Elaborate drafts before the deadlines and follow up of all the deliverables.
- ✓ Flexible assignments, parallel tasks, full time persons can adapt fast to changes in project workload.
- ✓ Promote the project and its interest to the right stakeholders to initiate the collaboration and have more easily access to information.

The Plan will be updated and changed according to the evolution of procedures and progress during the lifetime of the project. New releases will be delivered by Month 18 and Month 30.

1. Essential Documents

The fundamental binding rules that apply to the AfriConEU project are set out in the following documents, signed by all consortium partners:

- Grant Agreement (and its Annexes);
- Consortium Agreement.

1.1 Grant Agreement

A Grant Agreement (GA) was signed between the Project Coordinator (PC) and the European Commission (EC) before the project's start and by project partners through the Accession Form A. The GA is the legal document through which partners are made legally liable for carrying out the activities described in the Annex I of the GA, also called Technical Annex or Description of the Action.

The GA includes of the following parts:

- **Terms and Conditions:** contains specific information like the subject of the agreement, start date, project duration, grant and budget, rights and obligations of the parties, division of beneficiary's roles and responsibilities, among others. ***It is strongly recommended that partners read this document carefully.***
- Annex 1 (includes Part A and B): also called Description of the Action, is the main reference document for carrying out the agreed work. It is based on information from Part B of the original proposal, and it is specific for every project. ***It is strongly recommended that partners read this document carefully to understand the overall work programme and their specific role in the project.***
- Annex 2: Estimated budget for the action, including some additional information on the estimated budget, namely some specific unit's costs calculations. ***For your information.***
- Annex 3: Accession Form for Beneficiaries to the Grant Agreement, signed by partners. ***For your information.***
- Annex 4: Model for Financial Statement for Reporting Period. ***For your information.***
- Annex 5: Model for the certificate on the financial statements (CFS). ***Not expected to be used.***
- Annex 6: Model for the certificate on the methodology. ***Not expected to be used.***

1.2 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement (CA) elaborated using the latest version of the DESCA (Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement) model, which is a simple and comprehensive model Consortium Agreement, stripped of all unnecessary complexity in both content and language. This document establishes the rules that govern the relations between partners (for example: management structures and decision-making processes within the project, distribution of the Community financial contribution, rules on dissemination, use and access rights, settlement of internal disputes, etc.).

The CA is a legally binding document signed by all project partners. The European Commission is not a contracting partner to the CA, as the legal provisions which regulate the EC relations with the project coordinator and partners are laid down in the Grant Agreement (GA, see above). The Grant Agreement's regulations take priority over those of the Consortium Agreement.

During the project the Consortium Agreement may "evolve" and may be changed by agreement of all partners, e.g. to take into account changes in the project structure,

additional rules for exploitation or protection of generated knowledge, etc. Final decisions on the CA are taken by the Steering Committee (see section 2).

AfriConEU CA has entered into force on the 1st of February 2021 (the Effective start date) and will last for the whole duration of the GA (1st February 2021 – 31st January 2024). It is strongly recommended that partners read this document carefully and follow the agreed rules.

2. Project Management Structure

The overall management structure of AfriConEU project (Figure 1) has been designed to endorse links between partners, build and strengthen new interactions, especially by enabling and fostering the transfer of complementary expertise between the involved organisations, players and countries. Within the AfriConEU Consortium, each participant will take an active part in the efficient implementation of the project, and will cooperate, perform and fulfil, promptly and on time, all of its obligations as foreseen in the GA.

Figure 1 – AfriConEU Management Structure

Each of the specific roles and responsibilities are described next.

2.1 Steering Committee

The Steering Committee (SC) consists of one representative per partner and is the formal decision-making body of the project dealing with all key strategic project decisions.

Individually, SC members are responsible for the on-time delivery of results on behalf of the partner they represent, assure the quality of the work executed, monitor budgetary and technical results, and gather input for internal and external reporting and documentation. Finally, the SC also coordinates and manages items affecting the contractual terms with the EC.

Table 1 – Members of the Steering Committee

Partner	Representative of the Partner	Partner	Representative of the Partner
INOVA+	Miguel Sousa	STMLI	Irene Kalemaki
ECA	Peace Odili	ITC	Sasa Straus
YMH	Marilena Maragkou	BUNI	Edwin Bakalemwa
PBS	Catarina Reis	ATBN	Eunice Ball
OUTBOX	Richard Zulu	HAPA	Douglas Boateng
DPIXEL	Stefano Azzalin		

2.2 Project Coordinator

The Project Coordinator (PC) is Miguel Sousa from INOVA+, who has extensive experience in managing research and innovation-related European and international projects serves as the chairman for the Steering Committee (central decision-making body of the project – see below) and he is responsible for coordinating the project’s activities. The PC coordinates and manages those items that affect the contractual terms with the EC, as well as the technical and scientific activities of the consortium. The mandate of the PC is outlined (but not limited) to the following:

- (i) Accomplishment of project objectives within time schedule & budget constraints.
- (ii) Overall project planning and scheduling.
- (iii) Co-ordination of partners and organization of project meetings.
- (iv) Internal (among the consortium partners) and external (to the EC) reporting, documentation and financial management (with the support of the Project Management Office).
- (v) Representation of AfriConEU project and consortium to external stakeholders and initiatives.
- (vi) Communication with the EC.

2.3 Project Management Office

The Project Management Office (PMO) provides administrative and financial assistance to the PC to effectively coordinate the partnership and ensure the delivery of the expected results. This office is led by Ana Solange Leal from INOVA+ who has more than fifteen years of experience in running and managing European projects, including H2020 actions.

2.4 Quality Manager

The Quality Manager (QM) – Ioanna Garefi, member of STIMMULI and the QM Expert – Marta Coto, member of INOVA+ will be responsible for quality assurance processes outlined in this Management and Quality Plan. Both the PMO and the QMs support and are managed by the PC.

2.5 Innovation Manager

The Innovation Manager (IM) of the project will be **Rui Coutinho**, executive director of the Innovation and Development at PBS and former Scientific coordinator of the ME310 PORTO - Post-Grad in Product and Services Innovation that developed technology transfer projects with companies like IKEA Industry, Nokia, Ford, Generali, Phillip Morris International etc. The IM will be responsible for managing all innovation related activities of the project, with a special attention of capturing and assessing how new ideas developed by the project can be translated into new products, services and processes that will satisfy the needs of the different stakeholders. It should be noted that the IM will also take care of the project's Innovation and IPR Management Strategy, in close relation with the PC, and ensure that all background and foreground intellectual property of the project is meticulously managed.

2.6 Dissemination Manager

The Dissemination Manager (DM) of the project will be Marilena Maragkou from YMH, an international marketing and communication expert and member of the AU-EU Youth Cooperation Hub, being responsible to create, evaluate and monitor projects between Africa and Europe. The DM will be responsible for the design and implementation of the “Dissemination and Communication Plan” targeting to create awareness on the scope and activities of the project, coordinate the dissemination and sharing of ideas with external stakeholders, and ensure the widest possible diffusion of AfriConEU outcomes to its target groups.

2.7 Work Packages Leaders

The Work Package Leaders (WPL – Table 2) will be responsible for the coordination of the partners collaborating under their specific work package to ensure the quality of executed work. The WPL will also be responsible for:

- a. resolving day-to-day administrative, technical and resource problems within their work package;
- b. disseminating information relating to all aspects of the work to the other WPL ensuring smooth coordination of WP activities and;
- c. reporting to the upper levels of project management (PC, SC).

Table 2 – Work Packages Leaders

WP	WPL	Entity
Project Management	Miguel Sousa	INOVA+
Context and state of the art analysis	Eunice Ball	ATBN
Development of the AfriConEU Academy	Rui Coutinho	PBS
Roll out implementation and assessment	Ana Solange Leal	INOVA+
Community development and results uptake	Edwin Bakalemwa	BUNI
Communication and Dissemination	Marilena Maragkou	YMH

The responsibility of the deliverables to be developed under each of the WP, throughout the project duration, lies with the different partners as clearly defined in the Grant Agreement.

2.8 Advisory Board

The AfriConEU Advisory Board (AB) will be comprised of three leading experts in the field of digital innovation and tech hubs in Africa and Europe. AB members will provide us with their expertise on the needs and problems of stakeholder groups as well as with meaningful feedback on our views and project outcomes. Besides, AB members are expected to support the consortium accessing additional important stakeholder groups across Europe and Africa and drive the sustainable uptake of our results. As such, the following prestigious experts compose the AfriConEU Advisory Board:

- Eurico Neves:** currently the President of the Board of the Startup Europe Regions Network (SERN), an association gathering regional authorities in Europe and beyond for the promotion of startup-friendly policies, created under the sponsorship of the EC and the Committee of Regions. In July 2007, he was appointed by the EC for a term of 4 years as the representative from Portugal at the Business Chamber of the Enterprise Policy Group (EPG), an advisory board to the then Vice-President Antonio Tajani. In 2017 he was invited to become a member of the World Economic Forum's 'Digital Leaders of Europe' Community, that he joined in July of that year, having since contributed to the annual report "Innovate Europe - Competing for Global Innovation Leadership" presented in the Davos 2019 WEF forum. Eurico Neves has experience of leading innovation projects in Morocco, Guinea-Bissau and Angola and is currently a senior expert for the ASToN-Network project, gathering 12 African cities under the topic of innovative urban development.
- Gil Gonçalves:** Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto, the largest Portuguese university with activities in the realms of education research and innovation at an international level. Gil is currently the Chairman of the General Assembly of the National Portuguese ICT Cluster (TICE.PT), an association gathering industry, academia and research in Portugal. TICE.PT is actively involved at the national and European level on the definition and implementation of the Digital Innovation Hubs strategy. Gil is leading the participation of FEUP in the EIT Manufacturing, a knowledge and innovation community set up by the European Institute

of Innovation and Technology in 2019 and is the coordinator of the DIGITAL and InTelligent Industry laboratory, a research laboratory recently created at the University that brings together faculty members working in digital innovation projects. With an extensive experience in research and innovation, Gil has been involved in over 35 National and European RTD projects and studies to promote digital transformation in different sectors like manufacturing, health and agri-food.

- **Angelos Liapis:** currently the CEO of Konnekt-able Technologies Ltd. and Manager of EU Research & Innovation Development at the Decision Support Systems Laboratory of the National Technical University of Athens. He has worked as an R&D Director, senior R&D manager, active researcher and ICT specialist with experience in implementing and managing EC funded ICT projects (H2020, FP7, FP6, PSP-ICT, ENPI). His areas of interest and expertise include: Innovation Management, BigData, CSCW, Semantics, Web 2.0, eGovernment, eHealth, Crisis Management, Cloud Computing and Enterprise Interoperability.

3. Internal Communication

Appropriate communication measures will be taken to ensure that the flow of information and sharing among partners is consistent, regular and efficient. Considering the geographical dispersion of partners and different time zones, several channels will be used in the communication process, namely:

- i. mainstream electronic communication (e.g., emails, phone, skype, SharePoint, etc.);
- ii. virtual and/or physical technical/management meetings;
- iii. semester progress reporting (from partners to PC);
- iv. project workshops and other events.

3.1 SharePoint

A working online space has been set up within MStTeams for enabling communication and documents management and exchange within the AfriConEU partners. This SharePoint is accessible only to those invited and granted access and permissions are provided by the Coordinator team members.

The SharePoint is composed by several folder with specific purposes (Figure 2). The “Admin Docs” folder is intended to formal and contractual documents, such as the GA and the CA. The “Meetings” folder is to keep the agendas, presentations and minutes from all meetings (physical and online). A folder per WP is created to organise the information concerning the specific activities and tasks of that WP, including deliverables. Other folders may be created during the implementation of the action, as needed.

Nome	Modificado	Modificado por
Admin Docs	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
Meetings	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP2 - Context and SoA	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP3 - AfriConEU Academy	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP4 - Roll Out	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP5 - Results Uptake	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
WP6 - Com_Dissemination	17 de janeiro	Ana Solange Leal
Contacts_AfriConEU_Global.xlsx	6 days ago	youthmakershub
GANTT_Updated_08022021.xlsx	8 de fevereiro	Ana Solange Leal
Milestones & Risks.xlsx	15 de fevereiro	Ana Solange Leal

Figure 2 – AfriConEU SharePoint at MStTeams

Naming and numbering the project documents should be made in a consistent manner so as to identify the project, document type and the version. In order to identify a document version, the date should be used, with the format DDMMYYYY.

Name segments should be separated by _ and the acronym of the project that identifies the project should be included. For example, the draft version of Deliverable D1.1 produced on 15 March 2021 would be: **AfriConEU_D1.1_15032021_V01.doc**. When sharing a revised version of the document, the partner that has provided suggestions and inputs, should include its acronym before sending the new version to the remaining partners: **AfriConEU_D1.1_15032021_V01_ECA.doc**. When the document is in its final version, then the naming should be **AfriConEU_D1.1_DDMMYYYY_FV.doc**

3.2 Meetings

Seven consortium physical meetings are scheduled to take place on a semester basis rotating location (when possible, considering the current pandemic situation). The dates of meetings are sent per e-mail by the coordinator to the Steering Committee/Consortium members as soon as agreed. Meetings, whenever possible, should be organised together with other physical events of the project.

These meetings will constitute major milestones for planning, exchanging information among partners, assessing project progress and success (financial and technical) and for taking major decisions about project execution. Project milestones (Table 3) and risks (Table 6) will be

monitored during these meetings, and whenever required, adjustment measures/planning will be decided.

Table 3 – AfriConEU Project Milestones

No	Milestone name	WP	Partner	Estimated date	Means of verification
MS1	Establishment of the website and the project's visibility in social media	6	YMH	M3	D6.5 Dissemination toolkit and project's website submitted
MS2	Completion of research activities targeting the 4 African ecosystems	2	ATBN	M7	D2.1 State of play in African DIHs
MS3	Implementation of International participative design workshop	3	PBS	M10	D3.6 Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme
MS4	500,000 Social Media impressions	6	YMH	M12	D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan – Second version
MS5	Successful review and reporting acceptance	1	INOVA+	M12	Successful Interim review by the EC
MS6	AfriConEU Community with 500 members	5	BUNI	M13	D5.1 The AfriConEU community report
MS7	Implementation of local networking and knowledge sharing workshops	4	STIMMULI	M16	Agenda of workshops published on the website
MS8	1 st Webinar delivered	4	STIMMULI	M17	Recording of the webinar available in podcast
MS9	Implementation of International brokerage Event	4	STIMMULI	M20	D4.5 Brokerage event report
MS10	1,000,000 Social Media impressions	6	YMH	M24	D6.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan – Third version
MS11	Successful interim review and reporting acceptance	1	INOVA+	M24	Successful Interim review by the EC
MS12	Last Webinar delivered	4	STIMMULI	M26	D4.4 Webinars report
MS13	Completion of implementation of local networking and knowledge sharing workshops	4	STIMMULI	M26	D4.3 Networking and knowledge sharing events report
MS14	Implementation of 4 Design Thinking Bootcamps	4	STIMMULI	M26	Programme of the bootcamps published on the website
MS15	1st Online Masterclass delivered	4	STIMMULI	M28	Programme of the online masterclass published on the website
MS16	Completion of implementation of 4 Design Thinking Bootcamps	4	STIMMULI	M29	D4.6 Design thinking bootcamps report
MS17	Last Online Masterclass delivered	4	STIMMULI	M30	D4.7 Online Masterclass report
MS18	AfriConEU Community with 1000 members	5	BUNI	M35	D5.2 The AfriConEU community report

No	Milestone name	WP	Partner	Estimated date	Means of verification
MS19	Successful preparation of final report	1	INOVA+	M36	Final report submitted on time

Also, Monthly Monitoring Meetings will be held on every first Tuesday of the month, to observe and verify the work progress made in each of the WPs/Tasks. These meetings will help update project status on a regular basis, as well as having the opportunity to discuss operational and administrative issues on a timely fashion.

After each meeting, written minutes will be produced and circulated among partners with conclusions of discussions held and information about the next steps in the project.

3.3 E-Mail communication

To facilitate the recognition of electronic messages related with the project, a standard subject title is proposed, as follows: acronym of the project + subject [**AfriconEU | Meeting Notes**].

Partners are encouraged to use a MStTeams SharePoint to store files and preferably send emails only with link. E-mails should be sent with knowledge of the coordinator/management partners.

3.4 Reporting

In order for the Commission/Agency to verify that the project is implemented properly, the beneficiaries must submit any information requested, and in particular the deliverables and reports detailed in the GA. In this sense, two levels of reporting are to be implemented in the course of the action.

3.4.1 Internal Reporting

Every nine-months, partners shall report to the PC the progress made in that specific period, namely regarding main achievements, financial execution, deviations from plans and anticipated actions for the following period. The timing for this internal reporting is as follows:

- M1 – M9 – 1st Internal Report
- M10 – M18 – 2nd Internal Report
- M19 – M25 – 3rd Internal Report
- M26 – M36 – 4th Internal Report

3.4.2 External Reporting

AfriConEU project has two Official Reporting Periods when a periodic report (technical + financial) must be submitted to the EC via the Funding & Tenders Portal:

- M1 – M18 – Interim Report (Feb.21-Jul.22)
- M19 – M36 – Final Report (Aug.22-Jan24)

The technical report shall include an explanation of the work carried out, an overview of the progress and a summary for publication. Report on work progress is to be collected by WPL and provided to the PC, who will be responsible for integrating all inputs and produce the final report. Before submission to the EC, the report is to be validated by all partners.

The Periodic Financial report will include the Individual financial statement (Annex 4 to the GA), an explanation on the use of resources and a Periodic summary financial statement. It will be filled in by each participant in the Funding & Tenders Portal and signed by the Financial Statement Authorised Signatory (FSIGN).

3.5 Conflict Resolution

Conflict resolution procedures are included in the Consortium Agreement, in line with responsibilities defined within the organisational structure of the project. Conflicts will be solved at the lowest level possible, and preferably amicably. If an agreement cannot be reached at a task or WP level, then the Project Coordinator will mediate. If that does not work, then the Steering Committee will take a decision.

Negotiation and decisions taken by consensus will be the main tools to resolve conflicts. Should this approach and a majority decision not be achievable by the parties involved and the rest of the Consortium, an independent referee shall be appointed by the Project Coordinator. These conflict resolution procedures will be carried out in accordance with Article 11.8 of the CA.

4. Quality Procedures

4.1 Performance Indicators

For each of the Specific Objectives (SO) of the project, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been elaborated (Table 4) and shall be monitored closely to ensure the quantification of the outcomes of the project. To be noted that this preliminary list of KPIs shall be improved to cover all relevant aspects of each WP and proposed tasks.

Table 4 – AfriConEU Key Performance Indicators

Specific Objectives	KPI Description	Means of verification
SO1: Explore the digital innovation ecosystem in Nigeria, Uganda, Ghana, and Tanzania and analyse local DIHs needs so as to create tailor-made programmes for transforming local hubs into catalysts for digital transformation and entrepreneurship	In depth interviews with DIHs managers, entrepreneurs, policy makers from Nigeria, Ghana, Uganda and Tanzania to analyse the local innovation ecosystems.	>60 interviews
	Online survey of targeted innovation ecosystem stakeholders to records needs and challenges of DIHs	>200 responses
	Roundtable discussions in Nigeria, Ghana, Uganda and Tanzania with representatives from startups, SMEs, DIHs, government, investor networks etc.	4 roundtables – 40 participants
	In depth interviews with trainers of existing capacity building programmes targeted to DIHs from Africa and Europe	>20 interviews
	Interviews with trainees (i.e. DIHs managers and staff) of existing capacity building programmes targeted to DIHs from Africa and Europe	>100 interviews
	Report analysing the local innovation ecosystems in Nigeria, Uganda, Ghana and Tanzania	1 per country
	Number of DIHs Capacity Building programmes identified and listed in the project’s online data base	>50
SO2: Develop the Flagship Programme on Capacity Building for African DIHs and support thus their further development as well as their potential to drive the digitalization process	Capacity building sub-programmes covering DIHs business models, multi-actor approach, technology transfer, startups finance and digital skills	4 subprogrammes
	Capacity building webinars	20 webinars
	Online repository of capacity building resources and ready to use training material	1 repository
	Local networking and knowledge sharing workshops	12 workshops
	Online Masterclasses for supporting African DIHs potential/ Number of external speakers for each one of the topics (AI, IOT, etc).	8 master classes/min. 8 speakers
SO3: Develop the Flagship Programme on Trans-continental Partnerships Development and enforce cooperation on an equal footing	Online focus groups & number of participants discussing about challenges and opportunities for EU - Africa partnership building (T2.3)	3 focus groups & 30 participants
	International participative design workshop among DIHs, experts, investors, entrepreneurs etc. to discuss on the design of the Trans-continental Partnership Development programmes	1 workshop & 20 participants

Specific Objectives	KPI Description	Means of verification
between African and European DIHs	Trans-continental partnership development sub-programmes covering thematic issues such as investment and market opportunities in Africa, youth and employment opportunities etc.	3 subprogrammes
	Design thinking thematic bootcamps between DIHs and innovation stakeholders from Africa and Europe	1 per African country (4 total)
	International Brokerage event between DIHs, entrepreneurs, investors and the African Diaspora communities in Europe	1
	Capitalisation and celebration event	1
SO4: Organise and deliver capacity building, knowledge sharing and new partnership development activities among African and European DIHs and contribute towards a vibrant digital economy and new job opportunities for the benefit of both continents	Number of stakeholders reached through the engagement activities	>1000 (a min. of 60% from Africa)
	Number of participants in the 20 Capacity Building Webinars	>300 (a min. of 70% from Africa)
	Number of participants in 8 Online Masterclasses	>200 (a min. of 70% from Africa)
	Number of participants in the 12 local networking and training workshops	>200
	Number of participants in the 4 design-thinking bootcamps	>160 in total
	Number of joint projects developed during the bootcamps	>30
	Number of attendees in the International Brokerage Event	>200
	Number of connections for strategic partnerships made during the Brokerage event	>10
	Number of attendees in the Final Capitalisation and Celebration Event	>400
	Number of stakeholders and final beneficiaries involved in evaluation activities	>1000
SO5: Engage African and European DIHs, entrepreneurs, investors, and policy makers in a community of networked ecosystems that will foster the sustainability of the project results and the exploitation of opportunities between the two continents.	Number of stakeholders reached through the Online AfriconEU Community	>3000
	Connections made for exchange of knowledge through the AfriConEU the online community	>200
	Number of synergies with relevant trans-continental and inter-continental networks, projects and initiatives	>40

Specific Objectives	KPI Description	Means of verification
SO6: Foster the diffusion and uptake of the AfriConEU Academy within and beyond the targeted countries, contributing thus to the realization of the “AU-EU digital economy partnership”	AfriConEU Deployment Toolkit offering standardized resources for enabling any DIHs re-use them	1
	Policy roundtables and number of participants	4 / >20
	Policy recommendations Report and number of policy makers reached	1/ >100
	Exploitation and sustainability strategy	>1
	Dissemination and Communication Plan	1
	Number of unique visits to the AfriConEU website	>1000/month
	YouTube channel videos /views	10 / 5000
	Promotional Material distributed during project/external events	>1000
	Number of followers in social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube, Twitter).	>2700
	Number of Newsletters	>8
Number of Press releases	>20	

The KPI defined for the project will be followed-up by the PC and WPL to ensure the implementation of tasks is made in most suitable manner to achieve these targets and the overall objectives, thus maximising the impact of the action.

4.2 Deliverables Revision

The deliverables are the products of the project. Deliverables are also the evidence of the project’s performance and enable the Commission to monitor the project’s progress, implementation and impact. Deliverables are identified in the Annex 1 to the GA per WP and must be submitted according to the timetable specified in the table hereafter.

The AfriConEU project is built on a participatory and iterative approach to ensure the active involvement of all project partners in the development and production of the project’s deliverables. As a general principle, the responsibility for the content of each deliverable report is always with the author(s). This approach will serve as an internal quality review procedure to ensure technical value, accuracy and relevance of the reports developed.

The following process is proposed:

- Whenever relevant, draft deliverables are sent to all consortium members for feedback allowing them at least one week to reply;

- Each WP leader should ensure that the deliverable final draft is ready and circulated to the Steering Committee by the responsible partner **at least 2 weeks before due date** (see deliverable list – Table 5).
- Reviewer member should send their final comments to the partner responsible for the deliverable **within one week**.
- The partner responsible for the deliverable must then send the very final version of the deliverable **at least 3 working days before the due date** to the PC and PMO.
- The final decision on the deliverables is taken by the PC, and PMO is the person responsible for uploading the deliverable on the Funding & Tenders Portal at the **latest on the due date and informs the EC**.

Table 5 – AfriConEU Deliverables List

No	Deliverable name	WP	Delivery date	Responsible partner	Reviewer partner
1.1	Management and Quality Plan - Year 1	1	M2	INOVA+	All partners
1.2	Management and Quality Plan - Year 2	1	M18	INOVA+	All partners
1.3	Management and Quality Plan - Year 3	1	M30	INOVA+	All partners
1.4	Data Management Plan - Year 1	1	M3	INOVA+	ITC
1.5	Data Management Plan - Year 2	1	M18	INOVA+	ITC
1.6	Data Management Plan - Year 3	1	M36	INOVA+	ITC
1.7	Innovation and IPR Management Strategy (Interim)	1	M20	INOVA+	PBS
1.8	Innovation and IPR Management Strategy (Final)	1	M36	INOVA+	PBS
2.1	State of play in African DIHs: The case of Nigeria, Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania	2	M7	ATBN	INOVA+
2.2	Online data base with DIHs Capacity Building programmes	2	M6	ITC	DPixel
2.3	Lessons from existing initiatives and good practices for enforcing DIHs capacities	2	M8	ITC	ECA
2.4	Challenges and opportunities for trans-continental collaboration	2	M10	Outbox	ITC
3.1	Capacity Building Flagship Programme	3	M12	PBS	Outbox
3.2	Structure and training material for local workshops	3	M11	Hapa	Stimmuli
3.3	Webinars Content and Design	3	M11	PBS	YMH

No	Deliverable name	WP	Delivery date	Responsible partner	Reviewer partner
3.4	Inventory of capacity building resources and ready to use training material	3	M12	PBS	ATBN
3.5	Online Masterclass	3	M14	ITC	Hapa
3.6	Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme	3	M14	INOVA+	ITC
4.1	Implementation plan	4	M15	Stimmuli	INOVA+
4.2	Engagement strategy and activities reported	4	M15	ECA	Stimmuli
4.3	Networking and knowledge sharing events report	4	M26	Hapa	DPixel
4.4	Webinars report	4	M26	PBS	YMH
4.5	Brokerage Event report	4	M20	DPixel	INOVA+
4.6	Design thinking bootcamps report	4	M29	INOVA+	Stimmuli
4.7	Online Masterclass report	4	M30	ITC	PBS
4.8	Capitalisation and Celebration event report	4	M33	DPixel	YMH
4.9	Monitoring and assessment methodology	4	M19	Stimmuli	INOVA+
4.10	Impact assessment results	4	M34	Stimmuli	PBS
5.1	The AfriConEU Community Report (Interim)	5	M13	INOVA+	BUNI
5.2	The AfriConEU Community Report (Final)	5	M35	INOVA+	BUNI
5.3	The AfriConEU Deployment Toolkit	5	M36	Stimmuli	PBS
5.4	AfriConEU Policy Recommendations	5	M24	BUNI	INOVA+
5.4	Blueprint on DIHs transcontinental cooperation	5	M36	ATBN	ITC
6.1	Dissemination and communication Plan - First version	6	M3	YMH	INOVA+
6.2	Dissemination and communication Plan - Second version	6	M13	YMH	Stimmuli
6.3	Dissemination and communication Plan - Third version	6	M28	YMH	INOVA+
6.4	Dissemination and communication Plan - Final version	6	M36	YMH	Stimmuli
6.5	Dissemination toolkit and project's website	6	M3	YMH	ITC
6.6	Electronic newsletter – First Release	6	M6	YMH	INOVA+

No	Deliverable name	WP	Delivery date	Responsible partner	Reviewer partner
6.7	Electronic newsletter – Second Release	6	M12	YMH	ECA
6.8	Electronic newsletter – Third Release	6	M18	YMH	Outbox
6.9	Electronic newsletter – Fourth Release	6	M24	YMH	BUNI
6.10	Electronic newsletter – Fifth Release	6	M30	YMH	HAPA
6.11	Electronic newsletter – Sixth Release	6	M36	YMH	ATBN
6.12	Synergies creation plan and report (Interim)	6	M25	ATBN	YMH
6.13	Synergies creation plan and report (Final)	6	M34	ATBN	Outbox
6.14	Exploitation and sustainability plan (Interim)	6	M25	INOVA+	PBS
6.15	Exploitation and sustainability plan (Final)	6	M36	INOVA+	ITC

4.3 Project Templates

Partners will use provided templates for project documents and presentations in order to facilitate their production, guarantee the consistency and quality of AfriConEU image and ensure that all documents produced in the framework of the project carry the mention of EU funding in the requested format.

5. Risk Management

An initial identification of risks and related mitigation measures can be found in Table 6 and this list will be updated on *ad hoc* basis, whenever new risks are identified. Risks will be assessed separately and will be reported at least on a semester basis in the project internal reports. To perform the analysis and monitoring of the identified risks, the consortium will use a Risk Register Template (Annex 1) that will be verified regularly at consortium meetings to ensure actions are run smoothly and risks can be prevented or at least detected early in process.

Table 6 – AfriConEU Potential Risks

Description of risk	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Financial risks related to the implementation of the project	WP1	Financial management will not be limited to reporting, but it will include a close monitoring to be able to identify early signs of concern.

Description of risk	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Changes in the project team	WP1	The PC will require from partners to include substitutes with equivalent (or higher) qualifications and experience and inform them in detail about the project, their role and responsibilities.
Difficulties in data collection and research activities	WP2	The consortium includes partners already involved in the local innovation ecosystems to be explored and they will advise the design of the research activities. If difficulties arise, local partners will pay more efforts to reach out to the stakeholders needed for collecting research data.
Difficulties in designing tailor made training offerings	WP3	African partners will be actively involved in designing the training offering of the Academy. If needed, they shall engage more stakeholders from their local context to participate in the design process.
Ongoing <i>force majeure</i> (e.g. Health crisis) preventing physical capacity building, and partnership events	WP4	The consortium has already designed an online alternative for effective engagement and involvement of stakeholders in the AfriConEU Academy activities. In addition, the consortium has already foreseen dedicated activities for COVID-19.
Lack of coordination during implementation due to the large number of stakeholders and activities involved.	WP4	WP4 leader will be responsible to monitor all the implementation activities and ensure the transfer of all necessary information to local hub coordinators. In case of misunderstanding, personal meetings will be implemented.
Quality of events and number of DIHs, startups and other stakeholders attending activities are below expectations	WP4	PC and WP4 leader will continuously evaluate the processes. The PC will analyse results and take action in order to continuously improve the procedures. AfriConEU launches a new round of the activity, after evaluation, contact DIHs, startups, networks etc. directly in order to understand what is attractive & unattractive about the activities.
Low number of new partnerships among DIHs, startups, investors etc.	WP4	Identify the causes and explore new networks/contact to reach the target. Organize new matchmaking events.
Not enough evaluation data are gathered.	WP5	Monitoring and evaluation will start from the beginning of the implementation stage and will be conducted by Stimuli's expert team in large scale evaluation and impact assessment studies.
Ongoing dissemination may take more effort and resources than planned	WP6	The PC with the DM will continually monitor partners use of dissemination resources. Also, any opportunities for shared dissemination with other related projects will be exploited
Low visibility/impact of the AfriConEU Online Community in term of number of members, press coverage etc.	WP6	DM together with the PC analyse the media and marketing campaign developed, identify the causes and explore new networks/contact to reach the target. Organize new engagement activities to reach the target.

AfriConEU Risk Management Plan embraces the following activities:

- Identifying the key risks in delivering this project and anticipating how the risk will be managed within the project.
- Creating a risk reporting channel. Each partner should have the opportunity to identify perceived and/or real risks.
- Assigning who should be responsible for foreseeing potential project problems.
- Maintaining a risk database, recording emerging or potential risks and strategies taken to overcome these (Risk Register Template).
- Preparing mitigation plans for agreed risks. The purpose of the mitigation plan is to describe how the particular risk would be handled – what would be done, when, by who and how in order to avoid the risk or minimize the consequences if it becomes a liability.
- Balancing the costs of undertaking risk mitigation activities against the cost of exposure to the risk.

ANNEX 1 – Risk Register Template

Description of Risk	Probability			Impact			Risk Status	Mitigation Measure/Plan	Responsibility	Action Req'd	
	High	Medium	Low	High	Medium	Low				Yes	No